

Code Switching and Code Mixing in Modern Public Communication (Indonesian Sociolinguistic Analysis)

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ABSTRACT: This study seeks to examine how language is used in the social interactions of contemporary Indonesian society. The language use in question is an example of how modern culture in Indonesia interacts through code switching and code mixing. Using a qualitative descriptive research design, this type of research was conducted. The information referred to in this study is communication between contemporary Indonesians that demonstrates code switching and code mixing in modern culture. The speech in question takes the shape of a dialogue and includes words, phrases, clauses, and sentences that operate both as code switches and code mixers as well as having parts of both. Sources of data in this study came from the internet, namely previous research data, outstanding issues, and social media. Data analysis techniques were carried out with all utterances that show the occurrence of code-switching and code-mixing in the interactions of modern society in Indonesia. Furthermore, the classification and categories of the entire data are carried out. The data were analyzed by selecting and sorting out the forms and functions of code switching and code mixing in the interactions of modern society in Indonesia. After being analyzed and classified, the data is described and translated to find out the nature and applications of code switching and interference in contemporary Indonesian social interactions.

KEYWORDS: Code-switching, Code-mixing, Communication, Modern Society, Sociolinguistics.

INTRODUCTION

The main condition for the occurrence of a communication is the interaction between the communicators. Apart from using language, gestures, signs and signs, communication can also be done with other media. In the current era of globalization, communication media make a significant contribution to changing the world. Communication in this contemporary era can be done anytime and anywhere, across space and time barriers (Cangara, 2008). Human by nature as social beings always want to relate to other humans, want to know the environment around them, even want to know what is happening within them. This curiosity forces humans to communicate. Human nature to convey desires and know the desires of others, is the beginning of human skills in communicating automatically through gesture symbols, then followed by the ability to give meaning to each of these symbols in verbal language. Communication has shortened distances, saved costs, penetrated space and time. In addition, communication tries to bridge one's thoughts, feelings and needs with the outside world and makes one's horizons broaden.

The variety of languages of educated people, namely the world language of education, is a subject that people have often studied. It is this variety whose rules have been described more fully when compared to other varieties of language. This variety is not only studied and described, but also taught in schools (Anton M. Moeliono, 2017).

The general history of the development of the Indonesian language shows that the variety of High Malay at the beginning of the development period of the Indonesian language gained high prestige and authority because that variety was also used by educated people who later succeeded in becoming important figures in various fields of life. Educated community leaders are generally trained in these kinds of schools. That variety is used as a benchmark for the correct use of language. Its function as a benchmark raises the name of the standard language or standard language for it. This process occurs in many of the leading language societies, such as French, English, German, Dutch, Spanish and Italian.

Along with the development of technology, communication between people in the world is getting easier and faster. The influence of foreign culture is also more easily mixed with local culture. In linguistics, the influence of foreign culture or language occurs significantly and becomes a familiar phenomenon today. In linguistics and communication, there are something called code mixing and code switching. Code-switching and code-mixing are common occurrences in places where the routines bring together people from different regions and languages. Communication activities carried out alternately can create the use of two languages. The

occurrence of code switching and code mixing occurs because there are no rules that bind and prohibit the use of two languages alternately in speech events in every communication context.

According to Myres and Scotton (Lian Piantari) code switching is the transition from using one code to a different language code, while code mixing is the transfer of linguistic units, such as words, phrases, sentences, idioms, and greetings, from one language to another in order to increase the language's style or diversity (Kridalaksana, 2008). In linguistics, the relationship between language and culture or community habits is called sociolinguistics.

Sociolinguistics is a study that compiles theories about the relationship between society and language. Sociolinguistics comes from the words of sociology and linguistics. The study of language in relation to social circumstances is known as sociolinguistics. Sociolinguistics investigates issues with language attitudes as well as issues with language use. Thus, sociolinguistics refers to the application of linguistic data and analyzes it into other sciences related to social life, refers to social data, and analyzes it into linguistics (Thabroni, 2001).

A subfield of linguistics called sociolinguistics investigates how language and society interact and social factors, which are external factors. People who use language always vary in terms of age, gender, social status, economic status, education, religion, occupation and so on.

Language changes along with the times and is influenced by external, socio-cultural factors in society. This language change occurs because of the contact of a language with another language, which is carried out to adjust to and the tendency to innovate in a group in society.

In this modern era, sociolinguistics is more associated with the language of social media, or sometimes people call it the language of millennials. Society, or rather teenagers, often change the existing language to another language that is more contemporary. This phenomenon occurs due to environmental influences.

Based on the research focus that has been stated previously, the purpose of this study is to answer the formulation of the problem in this study which is formulated in the following questions:

1. What is code switching and code mixing in sociolinguistics?
2. What causes code-switching and code-mixing in Indonesian language?
3. What are the impacts of code switching and code mixing?

METHOD

This study's research design is qualitative, and it employs the descriptive approach. The instrument of this research was previous research data, outstanding issues, and social media. The data was collected in the form of analysis of the internet (social media and online news) and the researchers did not give any treatment to the subject. The researchers used this method to examine the code-mixing and the code-switching in modern society communication in Indonesia and the subject will be chosen randomly because the researchers only concern to the sentences that people used in their communication.

RESULTS

This section aims to answer the research questions in this study. This research will investigate the types of code-mixing or code-switching that people used.

Every human social activity, from a newborn baby's naming ceremony to the funeral ceremony for the corpse, a human will almost certainly not be separated from language use. Therefore, however, the formulation of sociolinguistics given by the experts' analysis of the issue of language relations with activities or social aspects will be included (Haryono, 2011).

1) *Giving Names to Children*

In the context of child naming culture in Indonesia, it was found that parents tend to combine two or more different languages in forming their children's names. The languages used are generally Arabic, Javanese, English, Chinese, Sanskrit, Indonesian, and Balinese. The meaning of a name depends on the meaning given by its parents. The same name can have different meanings (Nur Rini, 2018).

2) *Slang*

Language is a tool or means to convey ideas, ideas, opinions, feelings and thoughts to others, as well as to develop themselves and socialize with others. A language must have a clear meaning so that there is no misunderstanding in the delivery. There are several

variations of the style of language used in the community. The development of this language makes the style of language used by generations to change. Each generation will have its own distinctive style of language. The use of good and correct Indonesian is now starting to be displaced by slang, it will even feel strange if you use standard Indonesian for daily conversation because you feel accustomed to using slang (Azizah).

The image above is an example of a post by a Facebook application user. The post was basically written in Indonesian, but you can pay attention, there is the word "like" among the words in Indonesian. The word "like" is an English word, which Indonesian translation is "suka". The facebook user status above is an example of using code-mixing, the user mixes the English word with Indonesian words. This is most likely due to habit.

The image above is a screenshot of the opening of a news item on one of the Indonesian television stations. You can clearly see

the words "Headline News" in the image. That's an example of code-switching. In the world of modern journalism, a lot of code-switching occurs, such as "headline news", "breaking-news", "news-line" and so on. This is because their market is also increasingly diverse and multinational. Not only the people of Indonesia who can see, but the world. Language code switching in the world of modern journalism is common, and in the picture above, the language code switching occurs in the phrase "Headline News" which in Indonesian is "BeritaUtama".

DISCUSSION

Code switching is an event of switching from one code to another, so if a speaker first uses code A (for example, Indonesian), and then switches to using code B (for example, Javanese), then the event of such language use switching is called code switching, whereas code mixing is the insertion of elements of another language when using a language dominantly.

The occurrence of code switching is influenced by several factors, stated by Fishman (Aslinda, 2010), "who spoke, in what language, to whom, when, and to whom". In various linguistic literature, the causes of code switching in general can be mentioned: (1) speakers or speakers; (2) listeners or interlocutors; (3) a change in situation with the presence of a third person; (4) change from formal to informal or vice versa; (5) and change the topic of conversation.

Furthermore, in the opinion of Nababan (Dewantara, 2015), code mixing can occur due to several causal factors, including the following: (1) The speaker and the speech partner are communicating in an informal (relaxed) situation, (2) The speaker or speaker wants to show his or her education or learning. (3) There is no proper language for the language being used to indicate a member or a particular group. (4) The inability to look for standard words or expressions in a language. (5) The relationship of a language with the topic being discussed.

Meilan Arsanti, and Leli Nisfi Setiana, in their research, concluded that in the current era of modernization, the development of Indonesian is heavily influenced by foreign languages such as English. As a result of this influence, Indonesian people and netizens prefer to use the language of "social media" or what is often called the language of internet slam or prokem or better known as Alay. The bad impact is that the existence of the Indonesian language is increasingly being pushed aside by foreign languages. The charm of the Indonesian language is fading in the hearts of the Indonesian people. This cannot be tolerated because it threatens the position of the Indonesian language as the unified language, national language, and Indonesian state language. Therefore, there needs to be serious steps to maintain the sanctity of the Indonesian language (Meilan Arsanti, 2020).

Then, based on the results of Endang Fauziati's research, it can be concluded that the limited mastery of the English language has led the author of the Student Worksheet to use old habits (in Indonesian) into new habits (in English) by taking Indonesian grammatical elements for use in English. This has led to the emergence of grammatical interference. This grammatical interference includes mismatch of lexical system, superfluous expression. For example, in the sentence the weather felt cold and according to your opinion. Indonesian interference into English also occurs in several other grammar components such as the use of prepositions, parallel construction, the use of passive forms, the use of conjunctions, and the use of adverbs and modifiers to explain words, phrases and clauses. In relation to the factors that influence interference, the analysis shows that the interference from Indonesian into English contained in the Student Worksheet book is influenced, among other things, by the bilingualism of the author of the book, the existence of a gap between Indonesian and English Vocabulary treasures, and the carryover of Habits in Mother Tongue. The bilingualism of the speech participants, in this case the authors of the Student Worksheets, is the source of interference, because it is within bilingual speakers that language contact or contact occurs, which in turn will cause interference. The difference in the level of mastery of the language has caused the writer to experience difficulties in using English which he is less proficient at. This has resulted in bilinguals borrowing elements of the language they are more proficient at, in this case Indonesian (Fauziati, 2016).

CONCLUSION

One of the concentrations in sociolinguistics is code switching. Codeswitching is an event of using two or more than one language by the communicator in speaking. Code switching usually occurs in a bilingual social environment. Someone usually uses code switching or code mixing in order to be seen as being able to master many languages. From these opinions, it can be concluded that language switching events are influenced by several factors such as speakers, speech partners, situations, subject matter, presence of a third person, specific intentions and so on.

In language learning, sociolinguistics helps a teacher or student to determine a description of the state of language in the school environment and the language variations that arise in schools due to community patterns in language use.

The sociolinguistics community has identified three dimensions of the issue: social identities of the speaker, listener, and other participants in the communication process, as well as the social context in which the speech event occurs, such as whether it takes place in a crowded public space or a private space (a more private meeting).

Based on the results of data analysis, it can be concluded that there are two types of code mixing, namely Inner Code Mixing and Outer Code Mixing. Furthermore, based on the type of language, namely mixing internal and external code. The functions of code switching and code mixing include familiarizing oneself, changing the atmosphere to be relaxed, adding or quoting information, emphasizing, and giving praise.

Interference caused by code-mixing or code-switching occurs for several reasons, namely: (1) the speakers' bilingualism, (2) the habit of using the first language or mother tongue, and (3) the lack of new vocabulary acquired. In addition to having a positive impact on social life, which was mentioned earlier, this language interference also has a negative impact. The word (in the target language) actually has an equivalent in Indonesian, but modern society more often uses code-switched languages out of habit, maybe because they want recognition that they can speak more than one language. Unfortunately, interference is one of the causes of language errors faced by some people. Interference at any level is a "disease" because it can damage language, so sometimes it needs to be avoided.

REFERENCES

1. Aslinda, L. S. (2010). *Pengantar sosiolinguistik*. Bandung. Refika Aditama.
2. Azizah, A. R. (n.d.). *Penggunaan bahasa Indonesia dan bahasa gaul dikalangan remaja*. Jurnal Online.

3. Cangara, H. (2008). *Pengantar ilmu komunikasi*. Perpustakaan SekolahTinggi Ilmu Kepolisian (STIK).
4. Dewantara. (2015). *Campur kode dan alih kode pada interaksi informasi mahasiswa Yogyakarta : Studi kasus pada mahasiswa asrama lantai merah, jalan cendrawasih no. 1B*. JurnalOnline Sanata Dharma.
5. Haryono, A. (2011). *Perubahan dan perkembangan bahasa : Tinjauan historis dan sosiolinguistik*. Linguistika : Buletin ilmiah program magister linguistik universitas udayana.
6. Moeliono, A.M., Lapoliwa, H., Alwi, H., Sasangka, S.S.T.W., & Sugiyono. (2017). *Tata bahasa baku bahasa Indonesia*. Badan PengembanganPembinaan Bahasa.
7. Kridalaksana, H. (2008). *Kamus linguistik*. Gramedia Pustaka.
8. Lian, P.D. (n.d.). *Alih kode (code-switching) pada status jejaring sosial facebook mahasiswa*. <http://alih-kode-code-switchingpada-status-jejaring-sosial-facebook-mahasiswa>.
9. Rini, S.R.N. (2018). *Pemberian nama anak dalam sudut pandang bahasa*. Jurnal penelitian dan pengembangan humaniora : Epigram.
10. Thabroni, G. (2001). *Sosiolinguistik : Pengertian, objek kajian & variasi bahasa*. Serupa.id